

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Correlation of language skills on UTBK subtest with students' productivity skills

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 21(03), 2331-2342

Publication history: Received on 12 February 2024; revised on 25 March 2024; accepted on 27 March 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.21.3.0974>

Abstract

Written language skills are highly needed by students as an effort to increase student productivity skills. Through the Indonesian language subtest on UTBK, participants are tested on language skills to improve productivity which is very beneficial for life. This research aims to describe the language skills on UTBK subtest, as well as the correlation between the language skills on UTBK Subtest and students' productivity skills. This research uses a qualitative method since the data is processed using seven qualitative data processing steps. Data in this study was taken from 2024 UTBK prediction questions. Data analysis was carried out in two ways: content analysis of the questions tested in Indonesian language subtest, is PPU, PBM, and Indonesian literacy; and correlation analysis of language skills with students' productivity skills. This research shows that UTBK questions were divided into seven subtests. In the Indonesian language subtest, UTBK participants are given questions on how to write correctly and read meaningfully as an effort to improve their Indonesian language skills and Indonesian literacy. The criteria for good writing, referred to KBI and PUEBI, means complete understanding of grammatical elements, word formation, sentence structure, word choice, also correct use of spelling and punctuation. Through UTBK, students' language skills will be trained because students have to prove their knowledge through writing, both fiction and scientific works. This ability requires intensive training so that goals of common interest can be achieved.

Keywords: Language Skills; UTBK; Student Productivity Ability; Correlation; Indonesian Education

1. Introduction

Through language skills, a person will be able to understand the intentions, thoughts, feelings, ideas, facts and opinions expressed by other people. This also means that without language skills, it will be difficult to provide information to other people, be it feelings, desires, or even facts that have been observed [19]. Language skills can be interpreted as a person's ability to apply language [36]. In fact, language skills are classified into 4 groups: oral [8], written [8], production [19], and receptive [19].

Written language skills are passive language skills that do not require the sense of pronunciation or hearing, but only require the sense of sight. Written language skills include reading skills and writing skills [30]. Reading skills are defined as skills in understanding, observing, or thinking about things contained in a piece of writing [36]. Reading is done with the aim of obtaining accurate and credible information. The benefits of reading activities are sharpening thinking power, views, and broadening horizons [34]. Reading is also defined as a recording, decoding and meaning activity [10]. These three activities are processes that must be carried out step by step. Recording activities are defined as activities of associating sounds with words in sentences adapted to the use of the applicable writing system. This activity refers to a person's understanding and mastery of reading. This activity is also the most basic activity and does not require a background in language logic. Furthermore, Decoding is defined as the activity of translating graphic forms into words that can be interpreted. This means that in the second stage, namely decoding, a person carries out the reading stage by translating words and sentences, either in the form of narratives, graphics, tables or diagrams and connecting them with their initial knowledge. Meanwhile, meaning activities are the process of understanding the meaning contained in

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writing. This means that writing in the form of narratives or graphics, tables, and so on, gets a complete meaning based on language logic and the results of critical thinking. This meaning stage is the peak stage that requires analysis skills and deep and comprehensive meaning. This reading skill is also interpreted as material for carrying out the next skill, namely writing skills.

Writing is the activity of expressing ideas, ideas, facts and opinions obtained into writing. Writing activities include choosing diction as the initial foundation, then assembling it into sentences, paragraphs, and into a complete text [18]. As a tool for self-expression, learning and communication, writing activities require cognitive and metacognitive processes. This means that apart from involving cognition, writing activities must also include the writing process itself. The writing process is covered in four stages, namely the planning, preparation, monitoring and evaluation processes. Writing skills are categorized as advanced level skills, because this skill requires concentration and persistence in practicing it.

Written language skills are really needed by students. As a group that is considered intellectual by society and a group that is believed to be an agent of change, students have the responsibility to continue scientific traditions. This scientific tradition is the activity of reading and writing. This means that students need productive abilities to be able to produce scientific products according to their field. These reading and writing skills are useful in fulfilling the tasks given in lectures which are usually in the form of papers, term papers, case studies, or scientific articles. As a form of implementing the *tridharma* of higher education, students are required to be able to use language logic and think critically in solving various existing problems.

Based on data from the Indonesian Ministry of Education and Culture, in 2018, the number of new students was 1,737,308 students with the number of registered students being 8,043,480 students, while the number of graduates was only 1,247,116 students. In 2017, the Indonesian Ministry of Education and Culture also released data on graduates of 1,046,141 students from the total number of registered students, namely 6,924,511 students, with the number of new students being 1,437,425 students. Based on existing data, it can be concluded that the number of graduates is not comparable to the number of new students. Some of the causes are students' inability and lack of preparation in completing existing assignments. Therefore, students need productive abilities to create as a form of applying their knowledge and critical powers. Through productive abilities, students are expected to be able to provide new discoveries that can be useful for the wider community.

UTBK is a test that is prepared in such a way based on standards set by the Indonesian Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology (Kemendikbudristek). This test is carried out as an instrument for selecting participants who will enter state universities [25]. UTBK is designed to minimize the occurrence of injustice, inconsistency, and foster trust and togetherness among all registered state universities. There are three topics or seven subtests tested in UTBK to train reasoning and problem solving abilities, namely the Scholastic Potential Test (TPS) which consists of Quantitative Reasoning (PK), General Reasoning (PU), General Knowledge and Understanding (PPU), Reading Comprehension and Writing (PBM) [25], [24]; Mathematical Reasoning (PM); as well as Indonesian Literacy and English Literacy [24].

Written language skills are one of the materials available in UTBK questions, especially in the Indonesian language subtest content. Based on a preliminary study of the book *Libas 2000+++ SNBT UTBK Questions Scholastic Language Test Series* [23], questions were found that aimed to hone language skills. This is reflected in the PBM, PPU and Indonesian Literacy sub-materials, most of which contain good and correct writing and reading as an activity to understand what is conveyed in the text.

Research on UTBK has been widely researched and developed. The research with the title *Academic Ability Test Training for Class Improvement* occurred after training and administering pretests and posttests. Previously, UTBK was considered quite difficult for class. This research is included in classroom action research. The difference between this research and the research that researchers will develop lies in the method and independent variables. This means that researchers will use qualitative methods to develop their ideas and thoughts.

Research entitled *Analysis of Scholastic Potential Test Results as an Indicator of Student Readiness for the 2022 UTBK Test* discusses the relatively small readiness of class XII students at SMAN 1 Situbondo for the 2022 UTBK test [29]. This is caused by the environment of prospective UTBK participants and the perception that the questions are considered easy even though they require high reasoning abilities, so the readiness of prospective UTBK participants needs to be improved. This research focuses on increasing and instilling understanding in prospective UTBK class XII participants at SMAN 1 Situbondo. Research has also been carried out with the title *Introduction and Training in Understanding Scholastic Potential Test Material for Madrasah Aliyah Students* discussing the effectiveness of UTBK training which is

supported by appropriate modules so that it has an impact on increasing students' understanding abilities in answering previous year's UTBK questions which have been prepared by the training team [15]. Research with the title Increasing Student Learning Motivation through the Development of a Scholastic Aptitude Test in Facing the UTBK and SBMPTN Exams in the New Normal Covid-19 Era which discusses the provision of pretests and posttests as well as providing intensive guidance can provide improvements in UTBK tryout scores in 2022 at MAN 1C Sorong [32]. Research entitled Sharing Session for New Student Admission Selection (SNPMB) 2023 for Prospective New Students at SMA Negeri 1 Kafemanu NTT discusses how many students still understand that the 2023 UTBK consists of TPS and TKA [24]. In fact, the sub-materials tested consist of TPS and literacy so that training and service to prospective students is needed and has quite a significant impact. The difference between this research and the research that will be developed lies in the use of variables and research methods. This research will use qualitative methods with data in the form of UTBK subtests which aim to train language skills and link them to students' productivity abilities. Meanwhile, some of the studies mentioned above used the PTK method.

Another research entitled Practical English Grammar Training for UTBK SBMPTN Participants discusses training designed and implemented by a team of lecturers and students as well as various tips for working on English Literacy subtest questions for the first time, namely at UTBK in 2023 [3]. This research focuses on the English Literacy subtest and the content of the questions contained in it. The difference with this research lies in the subtests that will be studied. This research examines the Indonesian Language subtest which consists of Indonesian Language Literacy, PPU, and PBM.

Research has also been carried out with the title Asymmetry of Text-Based Indonesian Language Learning with State University Entrance Exam Competencies: Preliminary Study which talks about the discrepancy between the Indonesian Language learning material in schools and the material tested in the UTBK questions. Through this research, it is hoped that the Ministry of Education and Culture will create a new learning unit that is in line with the achievements in mastering linguistic aspects and text reasoning [20]. This research uses a qualitative method with the dependent variable being the state university entrance exam and the independent variable being text-based Indonesian language learning. Using the same method, this research will be developed to find out about the UTBK subtest which aims to train language skills, so that later it is hoped that these skills will be able to support the student's performance in developing their productive abilities.

Research on student productivity has also been conducted by M. Nur Rachman Nidhi Suryono, Rommy Esveldo Bhagaskara, M Aldi Pratama, and Arista Pratama in 2023 with the research title Analysis of the Effect of ChatGPT on Student Productivity [31]. The results obtained are that the use of ChatGPT has proven to be effective in increasing student productivity because it has various benefits such as making it easier to find accurate and clear information and making it easier to understand learning material. This research uses quantitative methods, while the research that researchers will carry out uses quantitative methods. Furthermore, the difference in research also lies in the dependent variable used.

Reviewing previous research that has been conducted by previous researchers, there has been no research that focuses on examining the content of language skills material contained in the UTBK subtest and connecting it with students' productivity abilities as intellectuals. This research is worth carrying out because UTBK participants need to know that behind the government's aim of holding UTBK as one of the entrance tests for state universities, the government also wants to provide provisions that can later be used as a means of supporting lecture activities. This provision is very useful to apply in the world of college and the world after, as a form of training in increasing productivity abilities. Therefore, this research has two objectives, namely first to describe the UTBK subtest which contains language skills, and second, to describe the correlation between the UTBK subtest which contains language skills and students' productive abilities.

2. Material and methods

This research uses a qualitative descriptive research type because the data in this research is processed using the following steps. (1) Building a conceptual framework obtained from preliminary studies, (2) formulating research problems, in this case there are two research problems, namely the content of written language skills as reflected in the UTBK question items and the correlation of UTBK question items which contain language skills with ability productive students, (3) selecting research samples. This research uses a purposive sample which focuses on the researcher's objectives in conducting research. (4) Selecting research instruments, carried out through document/literature studies, (5) collecting data from data sources, (6) analyzing data, and (7) evaluating conclusions [11].

The data used in this research is in the form of predictions for the 2024 UTBK questions. The data source for this research is a collection of 2024 UTBK questions obtained from printed books with HAKI or online via the website. The data collection technique was carried out using an in-depth study method on the 2024 UTBK prediction question items. Next, the data was analyzed using correlation techniques and content analysis on PPU, PBM and Indonesian Literacy questions which contained written language skills in relation to students' productive abilities. . The content analysis step is carried out by analyzing the discourse contained in the 2024 UTBK question items. The content analysis consists of three stages, namely: (1) determining the research design or model, (2) searching for main data or primary data (the text to be studied), and (3) searching for contextual knowledge and connecting it with other factors so that the research is not research that exists in a vacuum [1]. Meanwhile, correlation analysis is carried out by detecting dependency between two variables. Next, observe the existing relationship between these two variables. The final step is to determine whether there is a relationship or not and determine the direction of the relationship, namely in the same direction (positive) or in the opposite direction (negative).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. The UTBK subtest contains language skills

The issue of college entrance selection is in the public spotlight every year. This influences the development of the number of UTBK (Computer Based Written Exam) participants. Reporting from LLDikti.com and Dirjen Dikti.com, the number of UTBK participants in the last five years, namely there were 714,652 participants in 2019, in 2020 there were 558,107 participants, in 2021 there were 777,858 participants, in 2022 there were 213,406 participants, and in 2023 there were 803,852 participant.

Let's go back to 2019. 2019 was the first year that UTBK was held which was proposed by the Council of Chancellors of Indonesian State Universities (MPRTNI). Reporting from Padjadjaran University's page published in 2019 explains that this program is an effort to equalize opportunities for all students in Indonesia to get the opportunity to enter the best universities, not based only on schools that have a good reputation. Through this proposal, LTMPPT (Institute for Higher Education Entrance Tests) was formed - which in 2024 changed its name to SNPMB (National Selection for New Student Admissions) - as the only institution that has the function of selecting participants before entering state universities [20]. Apart from that, UTBK exists as a solution to the shortcomings of the 2013 curriculum and the 2017 curriculum which do not hone productive language skills, unlike KTSP (Education Unit Level Curriculum) which focuses more on training language skills in learning Indonesian.

UTBK is held not only as an effort to generalize and complement curriculum deficiencies, but also as an effort to select the abilities of prospective students so that they will be able to complete their education at state universities. This implies that universities strive for students to graduate on time. In fact, this reason did not come suddenly, but was based on unbalanced student and graduate data in previous years. This means that the number of new students and students who have graduated is experiencing an imbalance due to their studies not being completed correctly and on time. Based on data from the Indonesian Ministry of Education and Culture, in 2018, the number of new students was 1,737,308 students with the number of registered students being 8,043,480 students, while the number of graduates was only 1,247,116 students [22]. In 2017, there were 1,046,141 students graduating from the total number of registered students, namely 6,924,511 students, with the number of new students being 1,437,425 students [21]. Based on existing data, it can be concluded that the number of graduates is not comparable to the number of new students, giving rise to several problems such as a decrease in accreditation on campus which has an impact on the entire academic community [6].

As a standardization test to measure students' abilities before entering a higher level, UTBK is used by the government not only as a selection method, but also as a way to measure students' language skills and critical reasoning. These language skills are needed in everyday life to support the fulfillment of needs in college assignments and in the future world of work, thereby ensuring the quality of students who graduate from college.

In honing writing skills, UTBK participants are required to follow the rules for good and correct Indonesian writing. This rule refers to the refined general spelling of the Indonesian language (currently officially renamed KBBI) as well as general guidelines for the formation of terms [33]. In honing written language skills, UTBK participants are invited to think critically and deeply by paying close attention to the completeness of structures in various written languages. High concentration is needed in creating and understanding various written languages, because this variety is not bound by space and time so that if an idea is not conveyed clearly, it will give rise to multiple interpretations.

UTBK questions are divided into seven subtests. The abilities that will be explored are Indonesian language skills, literacy skills, basic numeracy skills, as well as reasoning and critical thinking skills. In the Indonesian language subtest, UTBK participants are given questions on how to write correctly and read meaningfully as an effort to improve their Indonesian language skills and Indonesian literacy. The criteria for good writing refer to KBBI and PUEBI, namely completeness of grammatical elements, word formation, sentence structure, word choice, correct use of spelling, and use of punctuation. This means that the government, through the Indonesian Ministry of Education and Culture, wants students' abilities to increase in the areas of writing and reading skills. Writing skills are honed through questions such as the correct use of affixes, the correct use of spelling and punctuation, choosing appropriate diction that fits the context, substituting diction by paying attention to the context of the sentence, and writing by paying attention to the effectiveness of the sentence. Several points on the 2024 UTBK predictions that explain this are as follows.

Perhatikan teks berikut

¹Sekarang olahraga sangat diminati semua kalangan, baik pria maupun wanita. ²Oleh karena itu, sepakbola juga tidak hanya diminati oleh kalangan pria, tetapi juga wanita. ³Akan tetapi, kegiatan ekstrakurikuler di sekolah masih membuka kegiatan tersebut untuk pria (siswa), ⁴Wanita (siswi) perlu diberi kesempatan juga agar ada kesetaraan antarsiswa. ⁵Untuk itu, kerja sama sekolah dengan berbagai pihak perlu dilakukan.

Penulisan kata yang salah terdapat pada kalimat nomor ...

- a. (1)
- b. (2)
- c. (3)
- d. (4)
- e. (5)

In English:

Pay attention to the following text

¹Now sport is very popular with all groups, both men and women. ²Therefore, football is not only popular among men, but also women. ³However, extracurricular activities in schools still open these activities to men (students). ⁴Women (students) need to be given the opportunity too so that there is equality between students. ⁵For this reason, School cooperation with various parties needs to be carried out.

The wrong word is written in sentence number...

- a. (1)
- b. (2)
- c. (3)
- d. (4)
- e. (5)

On this question, the ability to be trained is the ability to understand language logic. The wrong word is written in sentence number one. The reason is the illogicality of language. If you pay close attention, the word '*kalangan*' (in English it is circle) is an illogical word in the sentence. According to the KBBI, the word '*kalangan*' is defined as an environment, circle or arena. If we refer to the context of the sentence, then the sentence wants to describe a sports phenomenon that is of interest to men and women. The context in the text uses the word '*kalangan*' as a reference word that refers to men and women. Meanwhile, men and women do not belong to a circle or environment. Men and women are interpreted as a gender. So, the text should use the word 'gender' as diction which refers to the meaning of men and women, so that the correct sentence is written, namely '*Sekarang olahraga sangat diminati semua gender, baik pria maupun wanita*' (in English it is 'Now sports are very popular with all genders, both men and women').

Second question:

¹Perubahan iklim terhadap kualitas udara di dunia selalu dilaporkan oleh World Meteorological Organization (WMO) setiap tahun. ²Menurut WMO, musim panas tahun 2022 merupakan musim panas terpanas yang pernah tercatat di Eropa. ³Rekor ini kemudian dipecahkan pada tahun 2023. ⁴Gelombang panas berkepanjangan menyebabkan peningkatan konsentrasi materi partikulat (PM) 2,5 dan ozon di permukaan tanah. ⁵Ratusan lokasi pemantauan kualitas

udara melampaui tingkat pedoman kualitas udara ozon WHO, yakni sebesar 100 mikron per meter kubik untuk paparan selama delapan jam. ⁶Hal ini pertama kali terjadi di barat daya Eropa, bergeser ke Eropa tengah, dan kemudian menyebar ke seluruh benua. ⁷Selama paruh kedua Agustus 2022, terjadi intrusi debu gurun, yang sangat tinggi di Mediterania dan Eropa. ⁸Campuran suhu tinggi, jumlah aerosol yang tinggi, dan juga kandungan PM 2,5 berdampak pada kesehatan dan kesejahteraan manusia.

(Diadaptasi dari <https://www.kompas.id>)

Penggunaan koma dalam kalimat yang salah yaitu ...

In English:

¹Climate changes in air quality in the world are always reported by the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) every year. ²According to the WMO, the summer of 2022, it will be the hottest summer ever recorded in Europe. ³This record was then broken in 2023. ⁴Prolonged heat waves caused increased concentrations of particulate matter (PM) 2.5 and ozone at ground level. ⁵Hundreds of air quality monitoring locations exceeded the WHO ozone air quality guideline level, namely 100 microns per cubic meter for exposure over eight O'clock. ⁶It first occurred in southwestern Europe, shifted to central Europe, and then spread across the continent. ⁷During the second half of August 2022, there was an intrusion of desert dust, which was particularly high in the Mediterranean and Europe. ⁸The mixture of high temperatures, high amounts of aerosols and also PM 2.5 content had an impact on human health and well-being.

(Adapted from <https://www.kompas.id>)

The wrong use of commas in sentences is...

This question is an example of a question that aims to hone the writing skills of UTBK participants in the area of correct use of conjunctions. UTBK participants are trained to know and observe the correct use of punctuation marks based on the provisions stipulated in the KBBI and PUEBI in accordance with statutory regulations. Based on PUEBI, punctuation marks are divided into periods (.), commas (,), semicolons (;), colons (:), question marks (?), exclamation marks (!), ellipsis marks (...), and a hyphen (-). Reporting from jasa.kemendikbud.go.id, the regulations for using commas in the KBBI are as follows. (1) A comma is used to mention more than 2 details. For example, writing in the sentence 'A mixture of high temperatures, high amounts of aerosols, and also PM 2.5 content has an impact on human health and welfare'. The sentence uses commas correctly as a form of detail. Furthermore, in the same sentence there is also the use of commas when writing numbers. This is based on the function of the comma, namely (2) the comma is used before the decimal number or between rupiah and cents which are expressed in numbers. (3) Commas are used to separate main sentences that are preceded by subordinate sentences. (4) A comma is used before conflicting conjunctions, and is used after inter-sentential conjunctions. (5) Commas are used before and/or after interjections and words used as greetings. (6) Commas are used to separate direct quotations from other parts of the sentence unless they end with an exclamation mark or question mark. (7) Commas are used between (a) names and addresses, (b) parts of addresses, (c) places and dates, and (d) names of places and regions written sequentially. (8) A comma is used between a person's name and the abbreviated academic title that follows to differentiate it from an abbreviated personal name, family name, or clan name. (9) A comma is used between a person's name and the abbreviated academic title that follows to differentiate it from an abbreviated personal name, family name, or clan name. (10) Commas are used to enclose additional information or apposition information. (11) Commas can be used after information at the beginning of a sentence to avoid misunderstandings.

Based on the text, the first and third sentences do not use commas. Apart from that, the structure of this sentence does not require commas as punctuation to make it easier for readers to understand the meaning you want to convey. The second sentence uses a comma after the word 'according to...' in order to avoid misinterpretation. For example, if commas were not used in this text, it would be 'According to the WMO the summer of 2022 was the hottest summer ever recorded in Europe'. Without a comma, it is fine for the reader to interpret the sentence as 'According to the WMO, the summer of 2022 will be the hottest summer ever recorded in Europe,' or as 'According to the WMO, the summer of 2022 will be the hottest summer ever has been recorded in Europe.' These three sentences with differences in the placement of commas have quite significant differences in meaning. The first option is when a comma is placed after the word WMO, it can be seen that the person making the statement is WMO so that the statement conveyed is regarding the summer phenomenon in 2022 as the peak of summer in Europe. The second option is when a comma is placed after the word summer, then it can be said that the speaker, namely WMO summer, is making a statement that 2022 will be the hottest summer ever recorded in Europe. The second option actually sounds illogical because the word 'is' is interpreted as being, is, and giving appearance. So, if interpreted comprehensively, the second option states that 2022

will be the hottest summer ever recorded in Europe, even though 2022 is a marker of time/year, not a marker of conditions/seasons.

Next, sentence number four uses a comma as a marker for decimal numbers expressed in numbers. Based on the applicable provisions, the comma in the number 2.5 in sentence number four is correct and in accordance with the applicable writing provisions. In sentence number five, writing a comma after the word WHO and before the word namely is correct because the comma is intended as a sign used after the information at the beginning of the sentence to avoid misunderstanding. In the sixth and eighth sentences, there are commas used to mention more than two details. This punctuation mark is appropriate to use based on the provisions according to the KBBI and PUEBI. Finally, the seventh sentence uses two commas in one sentence. The first comma, after the words August 2022, is very appropriate to use a comma, because the comma is used after writing the date so that it complies with the provisions of the KBBI and PUEBI. This is different from the use of a comma after the word desert and before it in the same sentence, which is an inaccurate use of punctuation. This is because the words are not included in the conjunction. A word that is interpreted as a word that states that the next part of the sentence explains the word in front. If the sentences are separated with commas, then the sentence after rich will be an ineffective sentence because it does not have a subject in the sentence structure. So it can be concluded that the sentence that contains an error in using commas is the seventh sentence.

Third question:

Perhatikan teks berikut!

Seni lokal seperti wayang dan gamelan pun dipraktikkan dalam menyebarkan agama islam. Sunan Bonang, Sunan Drajat, dan Sunan Kalijaga melakukan hal ini. Melalui wayang, mereka menyelipkan nilai nilai keislaman dalam ceritanya. Melalui gamelan, mereka menciptakan lagu dengan lirik yang mengandung ajaran Islam. Lagu "Tombo Ati" ciptaan Sunan Bonang yang mengandung 5 nilai untuk mencapai ketenangan jiwa, mulai dari membaca Quran hingga memahami makna puasa. Hingga kini, lagu tersebut masih dikenal dan diingat dengan baik oleh masyarakat Indonesia. Selain Sunan Bonang, Sunan Muria pun menciptakan lagu ruhani dalam perjalanannya menyebarkan agama Islam.

Penggunaan wayang dan gamelan pun ada alasannya tersendiri. Pada abad ke-14, masa ketika para sunan menyebarkan agama Islam, dua bentuk kesenian tersebut dikenal sebagai alat penyampai pesan. Pesan-pesan terkait isu politik dan sosial disampaikan oleh sang dalang dalam pertunjukan mereka (BH Sutrisno, Sejarah Walisongo: Misi Pengislaman di Jawa, 2007).

Salah satu cara menyebarkan Islam yang menarik lainnya adalah seperti yang dilakukan Sunan Giri. Lewat permainan anak-anak yang diiringi lagu, ia mengajarkan nilai-nilai keislaman, sehingga anak kecil dapat bermain sembari mengingatkan ajaran Islam. Salah satu permainan yang ia ciptakan dan masih sering dimainkan hingga saat ini adalah cublak-cublak suweng.

Lirik yang berbunyi, "Cublak-cublak suweng, suwenge teng gelenter, mambu ketundung gudel, pak empo lera-lera, sopo ngguyu ndhelikake, sir-sir pong dele kopong, sir sir pong dele kopong," punya pesan moral mendalam. Lewat permainan ini, Sunan Giri mengajarkan supaya manusia tidaklah menjadi serakah dan menuruti nafsunya dalam mencari kekayaan. Semua harus dilakukan dengan hati nurani supaya diberikan kemudahan dalam mencari harta dan namun tidak melupakan akhirat.

Terakhir, ada pula asimilasi di bidang arsitektur. Bangunan-bangunan yang didirikan Sunan Kudus, seperti masjid tempatnya berdakwah, memanfaatkan arsitektur Buddhis yang sudah melekat dalam kehidupan masyarakat. Masjid bergaya lokal pun dibangun Sunan Gunung Jati sebagai tempatnya berdakwah. Berbagai cara penyebaran agama Islam yang diterapkan kesembilan penyebar agama Islam di pulau Jawa ini memperlihatkan bahwa penyebarannya bisa bersatu dengan nilai lokal sehingga glocalization pun terjadi bahkan sejak abad ke-14 di Indonesia.

Pernyataan yang tidak sesuai dengan teks adalah.....

Masjid bergaya lokal dibangun Sunan Gunung Jati sebagai tempatnya berdakwah.

- *Sunan Giri mengajarkan supaya manusia tidaklah menjadi serakah dan menuruti hawa nafsu ketika mencari harta lewat lagu cublak-cublak suweng.*
- *Sunan Bonang menyebarkan islam melalui wayang dengan menyelipkan nilai-nilai keislaman dalam ceritanya.*
- *Lagu "Tombo Ati" merupakan ciptaan Sunan Kalijaga.*

- *Ada asimilasi di bidang arsitektur.*

In English:

Pay attention to the following text!

Local arts such as wayang and gamelan are also practiced to spread the Islamic religion. Sunan Bonang, Sunan Drajat, and Sunan Kalijaga did this. Through wayang, they insert Islamic values into the story. Through gamelan, they create songs with lyrics that contain Islamic teachings. The song "Tombo Ati" was created by Sunan Bonang which contains 5 values for achieving mental peace, starting from reading the Koran to understanding the meaning of fasting. Until now, this song is still well known and remembered by Indonesian people. Apart from Sunan Bonang, Sunan Muria also created a song spiritual in his journey to spread the religion of Islam.

The use of wayang and gamelan also has its own reasons. In the 14th century, the time when the Sunans spread Islam, these two forms of art were known as tools for conveying messages. Messages related to political and social issues are conveyed by the puppeteers in their performances (BH Sutrisno, History of Walisongo: Islamic Mission in Java, 2007).

Another interesting way to spread Islam is what Sunan Giri did. Through children's games accompanied by songs, he teaches Islamic values, so that young children can play while being reminded of Islamic teachings. One of the games he created and is still often played today is cublak-cublak suweng.

The lyrics which read, "Cublak-cublak suweng, suwenge teng gelenter, mambu ketundung gudel, pak empo lera-lere, sopo ngguyu ndhelikake, sir-sir pong dele kopong, sir sir pong dele kopong," have a deep moral message. Through this game, Sunan Giri teaches people not to be greedy and follow their desires in seeking wealth. Everything must be done with conscience so that it is easy to find wealth and yet not forget the afterlife.

Finally, there is also assimilation in the field of architecture. The buildings built by Sunan Kudus, such as the mosque where he preached, utilized Buddhist architecture which was embedded in people's lives. A local-style mosque was built by Sunan Gunung Jati as a place for preaching. The various methods of spreading Islam used by the nine spreaders of Islam on the island of Java show that its spread can be united with local values so that globalization has occurred even since the 14th century in Indonesia.

The statement that is inconsistent with the text is.....

The local style mosque was built by Sunan Gunung Jati as a place for preaching.

- Sunan Giri teaches people not to be greedy and follow their desires when seeking wealth through the song cublak-cublak suweng.
- Sunan Bonang spreads Islam through wayang by inserting Islamic values into his stories.
- The song "Tombo Ati" was created by Sunan Kalijaga.
- There is assimilation in the field of architecture.

The third question is an example of UTBK questions which aim to explore meaningful reading skills. This means that UTBK participants are required to understand the reading correctly. UTBK participants are also required to find information and compare it so that they are able to differentiate between appropriate and inappropriate information based on the text. Apart from that, UTBK participants are also required to use their language reasoning to find appropriate information based on existing texts. This reflects that the ability to understand and explore the values contained in the text is very necessary. The aim is to avoid errors in understanding so that information that cannot be verified does not become a state problem.

3.2. Correlation of UTBK Subtests Containing Language Skills with Students' Productive Abilities

Students with critical and analytical thinking so that they are considered intellectuals [17] have the task assigned to them, namely as agents of change [9]. This assignment certainly requires the same amount of ability. It requires comprehensive critical reasoning [26] as well as language skills to express ideas and ideas [20]. Students live in modern circles who are increasingly aware of knowledge. This is marked by the rise of written language communication facilities such as newspapers, scientific journals, brochures and books [12]. Therefore, students have a responsibility to continue scientific traditions, namely reading and writing activities. The world's great discoveries were not born and spread

through word of mouth, but through writing. This article is used as reference material and the results are written into a complete article by combining previous knowledge and existing phenomena.

If we look at the reasons why students experience delays in graduating, information is obtained that one of the existing problems is that students are less able to complete assignments during lectures [35]. In reality, in university life, assignments are not at the level of questions 'What is meant?', 'Where is the location of the incident?', 'Who are the characters in the text?' and so on. Rather, assignments are given in the realm of understanding and developing knowledge which are expressed in the form of papers, term papers, case studies, and not infrequently, each course requires the production of a scientific article as a form of final semester exam [7]. This is an effort to implement the Tridharma of Higher Education [7], as well as implementing the essence of higher education, namely preparing students who have the knowledge, confidence, capability and self-readiness to complete their studies [2]. Of course, carrying out this task requires good ability and understanding to obtain complete information.

Language skills are closely related to the abilities needed in the 21st century. In its implementation, students often face challenges that require language skills, including the ability to communicate as a way to convey ideas, thoughts and opinions. In order to fulfill this need, the right kind of education is needed to hone this ability so that it continues to develop. Apart from that, language skills are not like arithmetic skills which can be done suddenly, in the sense that they can be done if you memorize the formula, but language skills require intensive practice which takes quite a long time and cannot be instantaneous.

Indonesia's young generation has limited literacy skills. A phenomenon that occurs in society is that many students in Indonesia who have graduated from junior high school are able to read but are still functionally illiterate with a percentage of more than 55% [28]. This means that the 9 years of learning that have been undertaken have not been able to train students' ability to understand and take advantage of the texts they have read. Based on the Alibaca Index in 2018, the National Reading Index in Indonesia is included in the low literacy category. In fact, the Indonesian law in Chapter III Article 4 Paragraph (5) which regulates the national education system explains that "Education is carried out by developing a culture of reading, writing and arithmetic for all members of society." It can be underlined that this law was passed in response to world assessment which places Indonesia in 62nd place out of 70 countries [14].

Very sad about this phenomenon. Not to mention that currently the world is shocked by technological sophistication which causes information overload. As a result, hoaxes easily attack without being able to distinguish the truth. Information will enter and become reading material without an information filtration process. This means that the reader or recipient of information only carries out the act of skimming without applying the concept of functional reading by taking lessons from this activity. Apart from that, the cultural phenomenon Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) is also a culture that has a negative impact on the psychological development of the younger generation. This culture exists in accordance with technological developments that are not supported by language skills, especially in the field of literacy. Literacy refers to the ability to read, write and digest information [13]. Literacy is not only based on reading activities, but literacy is interpreted as reading, calculating and writing activities that are based on language logic.

Through UTBK, students' language skills will be trained even before they hold a student degree. These language skills are closely related to students' productive abilities. Language skills are very necessary to train students' productive abilities. Students live as intellectuals who are required to always be creative and critical in facing existing competition. This competition can take the form of competition between students themselves, as well as competition that occurs in society. To face this competition, students need the ability to solve problems, always think critically, have creative power, have an innovative spirit, have a strong will (never give up), have long-term and short-term plans, have self-awareness, have an awareness of their abilities, and self-capacity, have accuracy and thoroughness, and have good emotional regulation.

Often, proof of a student's productive qualities is proven through the works they create. If we refer to students as owners and holders of scientific traditions, the more works in the form of writings, both fiction and scientific works, the more productive the student becomes. This ability does not just appear suddenly, but requires intensive training so that the goals of the common interest can be achieved.

4. Conclusion

The UTBK test is divided into seven sub-tests. It aims to assess proficiency in the Indonesian language, literacy, basic arithmetic, as well as critical thinking and reasoning skills. In the Indonesian language sub-test, UTBK participants are given questions about correct writing and meaningful reading to enhance their Indonesian language proficiency and literacy. The criteria for good writing refer to the KBBI and PUEBI, including completeness of grammar elements, word

formation, sentence structure, word choice, spelling accuracy, and punctuation usage. This means that the Indonesian government, through the Ministry of Education and Culture, aims to improve students' writing and reading skills.

Through the UTBK, students' language skills will be trained even before they obtain their degree. This is because students need the ability to solve problems, think critically, be creative, have an innovative spirit, have strong willpower (never give up), have long-term and short-term plans, self-awareness, awareness of their abilities and capacities, thoroughness and precision, as well as good emotional regulation. Students also need to demonstrate their understanding of the knowledge they possess through writings, both fiction and scientific works. These abilities do not come automatically, but require intensive practice in order to achieve common goals.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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